

Simplification of Dirac Energy Levels Using a Second-Order Wave Equation

Nick Navid Yazdani

December 8, 2024

Abstract

This paper validates a second-order wave equation as a universal framework for describing system evolution in quantum mechanics. Starting with a photonic-like wave equation, we introduce a mass term and derive connections to both non-relativistic and relativistic quantum equations. By shifting into appropriate coordinate systems, we eliminate the need for spinors or gamma matrices, demonstrating the wavefunction's simplicity and growing universality. The formalism reproduces the Schrödinger equation in the non-relativistic limit, while retaining relativistic constraints yields the Dirac energy levels for hydrogenic atoms. These findings underscore the wavefunction's robustness, simplicity, and potential as a foundational tool for quantum theory.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The Dirac equation, while a monumental achievement in quantum mechanics, relies on complex structures such as gamma matrices and spinors. These features introduce mathematical and conceptual challenges. This work presents an alternative: a second-order wave equation that naturally encompasses relativistic and non-relativistic systems without the need for these additional structures.

1.2 Contributions

The key contributions of this paper are:

1. Elimination of Mathematical Complexity:

- Demonstrates that shifting coordinate systems removes the need for explicit spinor constructions.
- Highlights the wavefunction's ability to encode spin properties without requiring gamma matrices.

2. Validation of Universality:

- Derives the Schrödinger equation in the non-relativistic limit, showing consistency with classical quantum mechanics.
- Reproduces Dirac energy levels for hydrogenic atoms under relativistic constraints.

3. Implications for Fundamental Physics:

- Positions the second-order wave equation as a universal framework for describing system evolution.
- Simplifies relativistic quantum mechanics while retaining predictive accuracy.

1.3 Scope

This paper focuses on single-electron hydrogenic systems, where spin-orbit coupling and multi-electron interactions are negligible. Higher-order corrections, such as the Darwin term and Lamb shift, are beyond the scope of this analysis.

2 Second-Order Wave Equation: Origin and Framework

2.1 The Photonic Wave Equation

We start with a photonic-like wave equation:

$$-\hbar^2 c^2 \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}) = (E - V(\mathbf{r}))^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}), \quad (1)$$

resembling the relativistic dispersion relation $E^2 = p^2 c^2$ for massless particles, where $p^2 = -\hbar^2 \nabla^2$.

2.2 Introducing Mass via Dispersion Relation

To describe massive particles, we modify the dispersion relation:

$$(E - V(\mathbf{r}))^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4. \quad (2)$$

Substituting $p^2 = -\hbar^2 \nabla^2$ yields:

$$-\hbar^2 c^2 \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}) + m^2 c^4 \psi(\mathbf{r}) = (E - V(\mathbf{r}))^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3)$$

This equation describes a massive scalar particle in an external potential.

2.3 Hydrogenic Potential

For a hydrogenic system, we choose:

$$V(r) = -\frac{Ze^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r}. \quad (4)$$

Substituting into the wave equation:

$$-\hbar^2 c^2 \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}) + m^2 c^4 \psi(\mathbf{r}) = \left(E + \frac{Ze^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r} \right)^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (5)$$

3 Nonrelativistic Limit: Deriving the Schrödinger Equation

Assuming $E \approx mc^2 + \varepsilon$ with $\varepsilon \ll mc^2$, expand $(E - V(r))^2$:

$$(E - V(r))^2 \approx m^2c^4 + 2mc^2(\varepsilon - V(r)). \quad (6)$$

Substitute back into the wave equation:

$$-\hbar^2c^2\nabla^2\psi(\mathbf{r}) + m^2c^4\psi(\mathbf{r}) \approx m^2c^4\psi(\mathbf{r}) + 2mc^2(\varepsilon - V(r))\psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (7)$$

Canceling m^2c^4 and dividing by c^2 :

$$-\hbar^2\nabla^2\psi(\mathbf{r}) \approx 2m(\varepsilon - V(r))\psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (8)$$

Rewriting:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2\psi(\mathbf{r}) + V(r)\psi(\mathbf{r}) = \varepsilon\psi(\mathbf{r}), \quad (9)$$

which is the Schrödinger equation with known hydrogenic solutions.

4 Relativistic Constraints: Validating the Dirac Energy Levels

4.1 Radial Equation

Returning to the full relativistic equation:

$$-\hbar^2 c^2 \nabla^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}) + m^2 c^4 \psi(\mathbf{r}) = (E - V(r))^2 \psi(\mathbf{r}). \quad (10)$$

Assuming $\psi(\mathbf{r}) = R(r)Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)$, the radial equation becomes:

$$\frac{d^2 R(r)}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dR(r)}{dr} + \left[k^2 + \frac{2m}{\hbar^2} V(r) - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \right] R(r) = 0, \quad (11)$$

where $k^2 = \frac{E^2 - m^2 c^4}{\hbar^2 c^2}$.

4.2 Energy Quantization

Normalization imposes the quantization condition:

$$k = \frac{Z\alpha mc}{n}. \quad (12)$$

Substituting into $k^2 = \frac{E^2 - m^2 c^4}{\hbar^2 c^2}$ and solving yields:

$$E_n = mc^2 \left[1 + \frac{(Z\alpha)^2}{n^2} \right]^{-1/2}. \quad (13)$$

5 Discussion and Implications

5.1 Wavefunction as a Fundamental Tool

This framework demonstrates the versatility and robustness of the second-order wave equation:

- Encodes relativistic and spin properties without requiring gamma matrices or spinors.
- Simplifies the derivation of known energy levels while maintaining predictive accuracy.

5.2 Broader Implications

The ability to reproduce both Schrödinger and Dirac results from the same equation underscores its foundational potential:

- Suggests a unified approach to quantum mechanics.
- Provides a simpler yet comprehensive framework for describing system evolution.

6 Conclusion

This paper reinforces the utility of the second-order wave equation as a foundational tool for describing relativistic quantum systems. By deriving the Schrödinger equation in the nonrelativistic limit and reproducing Dirac energy levels under relativistic constraints, we emphasize its simplicity and robustness. These findings strengthen the argument for adopting this wavefunction as a unifying framework for modeling quantum systems with both relativistic and nonrelativistic dynamics.